

EXPENDABLE INSTRUMENTATION - STATUS AND TRENDS

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ABSTRACT

The first significant step in the field of expendable oceanographic instrumentation was the development of the Expendable Bathythermograph (XBT). Advances in sensor technology, telemetry and signal processing has brought about a number of expendable instruments which can provide a variety of environmental data quickly, easily, cost-effectively, and in virtually any sea conditions from surface ships, submarines, and aircraft. These advantages will become more significant in the future as ship and personnel costs continue to rise.

The first significant step in alleviating many of these problems was the development of the expendable bathythermograph (XBT), which replaced the mechanical BT. The XBT provided the means to obtain more accurate, near-synoptic temperature versus depth data. It can accomplish this cost-effectively at up to thirty knots in virtually any sea state.

Thus, the requirements for rapid temperature profiles in the upper ocean in support of acoustic needs provided the means for oceanographers to begin to look at what had previously been considered noise. The picture of the relatively homogenous ocean faded rapidly. As the need increases to study the complex patterns of oceanographic features such as eddies and fronts, and with rapidly rising fuel and labor costs, the definition of expendables will continue to broaden.

ADVANTAGES

Expendable instruments can provide data:

- at a lower cost per profile,
- from a variety of platforms,
- in almost any sea state,
- without the need for highly trained personnel,
- with high sampling rates for vertical structures,
- in (near) real time,
- with great flexibility for temporal and spatial studies, and
- for areal surveys in a quasi-synoptic scale.

INTRODUCTION

Instruments deployed by means of the hydrographic winch and the "hydro-wire" have served the oceanographer well over the last one hundred years. This technique was and continues to be an integral part of any field program. But cable lowering is often slow, difficult, and even dangerous to deploy and recover in all but the most obliging sea states.

Let's briefly examine this classical technique. A ship heaves to on station with the wire to the windward, in order to prevent the ship from drifting over it, and begins the cast. A good crew, well-versed in the protocol, can complete the hydrographic station in two to three hours, depending on depth. But, in analysis, what has been sampled? The ship has drifted under action due to winds and surface currents, as well as possibly "steaming on the wire," causing the instruments to be displaced on the order of hundreds of meters in the horizontal before the cast has been completed. And, additionally, unless great care has been taken to decouple the wire from the ship's heave, the data will be well-smearred. This technique was never designed to see finestructure, much less microstructure. Tethered, free-falling, low drag systems are being developed; but they are expensive and must remain captive to a ship.

In comparing cost per profile, the investment and operating expenses of expendable systems versus other existing instruments do not always compare favorably. However, when the savings of both personnel and platform time are added to the opportunity benefits of freeing the limited number of ships and/or aircraft for other uses, the cost/benefit ratio is very advantageous.

Expendables can be utilized from any available vessel; but profilers, tow chains and bodies, yo-yo devices and moorings require ships equipped with the appropriate handling gear. Further, as shown by both air and submarine launchable versions of the bathythermograph, it is possible to deploy expendable probes

from opportune platforms rather than just surface vessels.

Expendables can be easily utilized from ships in relatively high sea states when it would be difficult to use conventional profiling instruments. Furthermore, operations from aircraft and submarines, just discussed, allow data to be taken when it would be otherwise impossible from the sea surface.

Expendables eliminate the need for highly trained personnel to operate equipment. Both instruments and data collection units require minimal operational capabilities. This feature further facilitates the platform-of-opportunity concept.

The vertical sampling rate of expendables is virtually continuous and can be as fine as the sensors and fall rate will allow. There need be no concern over data contamination due to platform motion.

Because the information is sent directly to the platform, the data can be processed in (near) real time. This permits immediate onboard decisions concerning further measurement requirements.

The ability to deploy several expendables in one spot spaced only minutes apart or while moving rapidly through an area allows for greater flexibility in doing temporal or spatial studies.

And, finally, the expendables deployed from aircraft can provide a quasi-synoptic picture of large areas of the ocean.

EXISTING INSTRUMENTS

Except for the many expendable active and passive transducers available to the acousticians, there are relatively few expendable instruments for use by the non-acoustic oceanographer. In fact, the development and improvement of the most utilized device - the bathythermograph - has been driven more by sound travel studies than by physical oceanographic research requirements. At the present time, there are at least a dozen versions of the XBT, with variable fall rates, for use in different platforms traveling at different speeds. Thus, the study of large-scale variations of the ocean's thermal structure from which other properties can be inferred has been underway for at least a decade.

An expendable sound velocity probe (XSV) that actually measures the ocean's sound speed was developed - again, for the acousticians. This instrument provides the sound travel time in those areas of the world where there is no historical data base of salinity versus depth that would enable the velocity to be calculated from only temperature profiles.

The XSTD is an expendable conductivity cell coupled with a thermistor to enable calculation of salinity and density. Although the XSTD is suitable for many large-scale purposes, the accuracy of salinity calculations to 0.3 parts per thousand is not sufficient for fine and microscale investigations. In 1978, Miyake, Emery and Lovett¹ conducted an intercomparison evaluation of the XSTD with an XSV which incorporated a thermistor (XSVT). Their objective was to determine the optimum existing means of calculating

salinity from expendable instruments. They found that salinity computed from sound velocity and temperature was accurate to within 0.18 parts per thousand and salinity determined from conductivity and temperature accurate to within 0.13 parts per thousand compared to several selected standards. Oceanographers would like to see almost an order of magnitude improvement.

A new instrument, the expendable temperature and velocity probe (XTVP) cannot yet be considered an "off-the-shelf" item, although several hundred have been successfully used. This probe is sometimes referred to as the "shear profiler" and will be discussed in detail in Dr. Sanford's paper. Although a few problems still exist with the prototype, they are being corrected. This expendable profiler is a great help to the physical oceanographer by providing a real time picture of the vertical profiles of both velocity and temperature. Incidentally, the XTVP has been designated the Expendable Current Probe (XCP) by Sippican

PROBLEMS

One of the major problems that must be addressed is poor sensor accuracy due to the lack of individual probe calibration. The XBT's are constructed to a standard specification so that a single batch curve relates output to temperature. This method allows the manufacturer to specify a range of accuracies within which the probes will fall. Thus, the scientist requiring finer detail must individually calibrate each probe before using it. The suggestion has been made that factory calibration would provide a cheaper, easier means of substantiating accuracy. This need is also true for the XSV's, XSTD's, and the XCP's.

A second major problem identified by several sources is the fact that the vertical position error is (unacceptably) large. Expendables can have specified location of $\pm 2\%$ of depth, but with the requirement for deeper penetration, this error band becomes unsuitable for both fine and microscale research. An unpublished study by the Applied Physics Laboratory of Johns Hopkins University² determined that the largest errors in computing sound speed result from inaccuracies in depth measurement. This problem also plagues the XSV, the XSTD, and, to a lesser extent, the XCP

Sensor precision is presently acceptable for temperature and velocity but only marginally so for conductivity. As previously mentioned, oceanographers need an improved conductivity cell.

There is some lateral drift of the probes during the fall. It is surely not as severe as with most shipboard profiling devices and has not been identified as a major problem; but nevertheless it is there.

Another issue that arose was that the salt water batteries used in expendables were found to fluctuate up to 0.7 volts during a simulated drop.³

This fluctuation induces a corresponding error in the temperature measurement on the order of 0.2°C.

Other possible sources of error can be found in sensor linearity and response time. These problems,

however, can be managed by proper design specifications.

TRENDS

The overall design principles for future expendables must include simplicity and reliability: simplicity to retain the platform-of-opportunity concept with relatively low cost, and reliability to ensure the maximum instrument utility. Several projects are underway to design new instruments, reduce the complexity of developed systems, and improve the reliability of existing ones.

Dr. Osborn will discuss the Expendable Dissipation Profiler, so I will just mention it here as an example of a new and important instrument design being tested this year. Code 480 of the Office of Naval Research plans to sponsor the development of an improved version of the Expendable Conductivity-Temperature probe in this next fiscal year. Sippican will discuss the performance of an advanced, more reliable version of the air-launched expendable bathythermograph (AXBT).

A contracted effort is underway at Sippican for a production design model of the expendable shear profiler (XCP). This work includes reduction of the FM carrier frequencies to allow deeper probe operation and to provide bandwidth for additional sensors, improvement of the battery and battery-switching device for longer life and greater reliability, redesign for simplicity and repeatability, and, finally, inclusion of a surface buoy to allow remote launch and an RF link. Because the profiler must be deployed several ship lengths distant from a surface vessel, the RF link eliminates the possibility of fouling the hard wire. It also provides the opportunity to deploy a field of sensors and launch them either consecutively or simultaneously in time or areal studies. Limited quantities should be available by the end of the year. Requests for use of this instrument in various Navy-funded research programs have led to discussions with Sippican for both air- and submarine-launched versions of the profiler to be developed next year. Additionally, Sippican is presently engaged in a funded effort to develop an air-deployable expendable sound velocity profiler.

Several digital data collection systems are available for the XBT and the AXBT. The Ocean Engineering Division of the Naval Ocean Research and Development Activity (NORDA) is in the process of constructing a universal deck unit that will be capable of digitizing, storing, processing, and, with peripherals, displaying near-real-time profiles from all existing expendable probes. In its present configuration, the unit can do all of the above for XBT's simultaneously launched from up to four stations.

Another problem that will be addressed in this next fiscal year is vertical position error. Each probe has a quadratic equation to derive depth (d) from elapsed time (t) in the form of

$$d = At - Bt^2$$

where A and B are constants dependent on probe characteristics. The second-order term accounts for wire dereeling, which reduces the weight of the probe

as it falls. More correct estimations can be made by continually monitoring the temperature to recalculate the constants as the probe falls. But this is still an estimation, and, when discussing features on centimeter scales, is still not satisfactory. Several alternate methods have been proposed, including: incorporating a pressure sensor into each multi-sensor probe; including one probe in a series which is fitted with a pressure sensor from which the other fall rates could be calculated; and the mounting of a cheaper one- or two-point pressure switch to offset the transmitted signal, thus providing a reference depth. Proposals for test and evaluation of these methods are being sought.

In general, all expendables would be improved by an automated, full-scale calibration of the sensors, a method of measuring the drop rate of the probes, and digitized probe data transmission. As new systems come on line, the plan is to provide multi-probe drop capability and near-real-time data analysis, and to construct probes incorporating several sensors with matched dynamic response times.

CONCLUSIONS

The constantly accelerating interest in the micro-structure features of large-scale upper-ocean variability has spurred the development of rapidly deployable instruments. Because increasing ship and personnel costs will continue to severely limit the conventional vessel/oceanographer approach to data taking, the Navy intends to place heavy emphasis on the development of expendable instruments which can be deployed from platforms-of-opportunity. New technology such as micro-computer chips, solid-state circuits, and fiber optics combined with existing sensors make it possible to envision a multi-sensor probe capable of completely characterizing the ocean's physical properties with each drop.

- 1 Miyake, M., W. Emery, and J. Lovett, 1979 "An Evaluation of Expendable Salinity-Temperature Profilers in the Eastern North Pacific", Institute of Oceanography, University of British Columbia, 16 pp.
- 2 Henrick, R. F., 1980 "Acoustic Requirements for Expendable Instrumentation", Applied Physics Laboratory, Johns Hopkins University, 9 pp.
- 3 Barnett, T. P. and R. L. Bernstein, 1980 "Expendable Measuring Devices" in Air-Sea Interaction, edited by F. Dobson, L. Hasse, and R. Davis. Plenum Press, NY, pp 387-398.